

Down the polyhalide path[†]

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Kinetic and mechanistic studies of oxidation by several quaternary ammonium salts of polyhalides, reported from this laboratory, are reviewed. Various kinetic and activation parameters have been reported. The effects of solvent composition, isotopic labeling and isotope composition of solvent have been discussed. Correlation analysis of the reactivity has been emphasized. Suitable mechanisms have been proposed.

It was in the early 1990s that we got interested in kinetics and mechanism of oxidations by polyhalides. A paper by Gnanadoss and Vijayalakshmi¹ on the oxidation of alcohols of pyridinium hydrobromide perbromide (PHPB), or more correctly pyridinium tribromide kindled our interest in this field. During the course of our investigation of the reactions of PHPB, we came across the excellent work of Okamoto *et al.*² on the preparative and synthetic aspects of a large number of quaternary ammonium polyhalides. Similarly, a new brominating and oxidizing reagent, hexamethylenetetramine-bromine, was reported in 1994 by Yavari and Shaabani³. These compounds are more suitable than molecular halogens because of their solid nature, ease of handling, stability, selectivity and excellent product yields. We describe below the results of our endeavor of the last one-decade with the polyhalides.

Pyridinium hydrobromide perbromide (PHPB)

The oxidation of aliphatic primary⁴ and secondary⁵ alcohols, substituted benzyl alcohols⁶ and diols⁷ by PHPB in aqueous acetic acid has been reported. The reactions are first order with respect to PHPB. Michaelis-Menten type kinetics were observed with respect to the hydroxy compounds except that of the secondary alcohols which exhibited a first order dependence on the alcohol. Oxidation of deuteriated ethanol, benzhydrol and benzyl alcohol indicated the presence of large primary kinetic isotope effects. This confirmed the cleavage of the α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step. The oxidation of deuteriated ethanediol, however, did not show any kinetic isotope effect. The oxidation of vicinal-diols yielded the products arising out of glycol-bond fission. Non-vicinal-diols and other alcohols were oxidized to the corresponding carbonyl compounds. The oxidation of aliphatic alcohols correlated well with Pavelich-Taft⁸ equation. The rates of oxidation of *meta*- and *para*-

substituted benzyl alcohols were correlated with Taft's dual substituent-parameter (DSP) equation⁹. The *ortho*-compounds correlated best with Charton's triparametric equation¹⁰. The polar reaction constants have large negative values indicating the presence of an electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state of the rate-determining step. The reactions are subjected to a steric acceleration by *ortho*-substituents and alkyl groups. A mechanism involving formation of an intermediate complex in a rapid pre-equilibrium and its subsequent decomposition in the slow step has been proposed for the oxidation of the alcohols and non-vicinal-diols (Scheme 1). It has been suggested that in the oxidation of secondary alcohols, the equilibrium constant has a small value and, therefore, is not reflected in the rate-

Scheme 1

law. The diols undergo glycol-bond fission in the rate-determining step (Scheme 2).

Varshney *et al.*¹¹ reported the oxidation of three lower oxyacids of phosphorus by PHPB in aqueous acetic acid solutions. The oxidation of deuteriated phosphinic and phosphorous acids exhibited substantial primary kinetic isotope effects. The reaction is first order with respect to

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Scheme 2

Scheme 3

both the oxyacids and PHPB. Transfer of a hydride ion from the pentacoordinated form of the oxyacids to PHPB, in the rate-determining step, has been proposed.

Aparna *et al.*¹² reported the oxidation of some α -hydroxy acids by PHPB in 3 : 7 (v/v) acetic acid-water mixture. The reaction is first order each in PHPB and the hydroxy acid. The oxidation of mandelic acid showed a substantial primary kinetic isotope effects. A mechanism involving a hydride ion transfer to the oxidant is proposed.

Devi *et al.*¹³ reported the kinetics of the oxidation of some aliphatic aldehydes in aqueous acetic acid solution. The kinetics of the reaction was similar to that observed in the oxidation of alcohols^{4,5}. Role of the hydrate form of aldehydes in the process of oxidation was discussed. Transfer of a hydride ion from the hydrate form of aldehyde to PHPB via an intermediate complex, in the rate-determining step has been proposed (*cf.* Scheme 1).

Devi *et al.*¹⁴ reported the oxidation of α -amino acids by PHPB in 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water mixture. The reaction is first order with respect to PHPB. The order was more than one and less than two with respect to some of the amino acids, while others exhibited a second order dependence. The oxidation of perdeuteriogylicine showed the absence of a kinetic isotope effect. The reaction is susceptible to both the polar and steric effects of the substituents. It has been proposed that a 2 : 1 complex of the amino acid and PHPB is formed in a rapid pre-equilibrium, which then decomposes in the slow step to form the corresponding aldimine (Scheme 3).

The oxidation of formic and oxalic acids¹⁵ by PHPB exhibited a Michaelis-Menten type kinetics with respect to the organic acids. An analysis of the solvent composition effect indicated that the transition state is more polar than the reactant. It has been proposed that formic acid forms an acyclic intermediate complex in the pre-equilibrium while the intermediate in the case of oxalic acid is cyclic in nature. These intermediates disproportionate in the rate-determining step to carbon dioxide.

The oxidation of organic sulfides¹⁶ exhibited second order kinetics, first with respect to each the sulfide and PHPB. The rates of oxidation of aryl methyl sulfides were analyzed in terms of Charton's LDR/LDRS equations¹⁷, whereas those of alkyl phenyl sulfides correlated best with Pavelich-Taft's equation⁸. The polar reaction constants are negative. The experimental results have been explained on the basis of a rate-determining attack of a PHPB molecule on the sulfide to yield a halogenosulfonium cation (Scheme 4). The oxidation of methionine, a sulfur-containing amino acid, has been studied¹⁸. Methionine behave as a sulfide towards PHPB. The experimental results and the proposed mechanism are similar to those reported for the other sulfides¹⁶.

The oxidation monosubstituted benzaldehydes¹⁹ by PHPB were studied in aqueous acetic acid solution. The main product of the oxidation is the corresponding benzoic acid. The reaction is first order with respect to each of the aldehyde and PHPB. The oxidation of deuteriated benzaldehyde (PhCDO) exhibited the presence of a

Scheme 4

substantial kinetic isotope effect. This confirmed the cleavage of aldehydic C-H bond in the rate-determining step. The rates of oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes were correlated in terms of Charton's LDR/LDRS equations. The polar reaction constants are negative pointing to an electron-deficient reaction centre in the rate-determining step. A rate-determining hydride ion transfer from the aromatic aldehyde to PHPB, generating an acyl cation, has been suggested.

Benzyltrimethylammonium dichloroiodate (BTMACI)

BTMACI is found to be a useful reagent for iodination and chloriodination of many organic compounds. BTMACI is completely soluble in dichloromethane only and is slightly soluble in acetic acid at room temperature. However, an addition of zinc chloride makes this reagent soluble in acetic acid.

The oxidation reactions of some thioacids²⁰, lower oxyacids of phosphorus²¹, substituted benzyl alcohols²², aliphatic aldehydes²³, diols²⁴, substituted benzaldehydes²⁵, aliphatic alcohols²⁶ and of formic and oxalic acids²⁷ by BTMACI have been studied in acetic acid. The reactions are of first order with respect to each – the reductant, BTMACI and zinc chloride. In the presence of zinc chloride, BTMACI is reported² to produce an active species (A),

From the data on the solubility of BTMACI in the absence and presence of zinc chloride, the value of the equilibrium constant (K_1) comes out²⁶ to be *ca.* 2400 mol⁻¹ dm³. This indicates that even at the lowest concentration of zinc chloride used, almost whole of BTMACI will be in the form

of complex (A). The linear increase in the rate with an increase in the concentration of zinc chloride points to a further complexation [eqn. (2)]. The role of zinc chloride is to coordinate with ICl_2^- ,

In the complexes (A) and (B), the formal oxidation state of iodine is +1. The observed dependence on the concentration of zinc chloride indicates that the equilibrium between (A) and (B) is rapid, that the equilibrium constant, K_2 is small and the reaction is not complete even at high concentration of zinc chloride, and that only complex (B) is reactive. BTMACI can also undergo the following reaction [eqn. (3)],

But the observed small rate-enhancing effect of benzyltrimethylammonium chloride suggests that iodine monochloride is not involved in the oxidation process. Therefore, (B) is the only reactive oxidizing species in the oxidation of the organic compounds. The formation of the complex was supported by the spectral studies also.

The oxidation of deuteriated benzyl alcohol²², phosphinic acid²¹, phosphorous acid²¹, acetaldehyde²³, ethanol²⁶ and formic acid²⁷ indicated the presence of substantial kinetic isotope effects. This confirms the cleavage of the corresponding C-H or P-H bond in the rate-determining step. The effect of substituent in the oxidation of benzyl alcohols was analyzed in terms of Charton's LDR/LDRS equations¹⁷. The polar reaction constants are negative, indicating the presence of an electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state of rate-determining step. The reaction is subject to a steric acceleration by the *ortho*-groups. Similarly, the oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes showed an excellent correlation with Taft's σ^* values with negative reactions constants.

It has been proposed that the oxidation of alcohols, the aldehydes and the oxyacids of phosphorus proceeded through a hydride-ion transfer to the oxidant. The rate-determining step in the oxidation of the thioacids involved the formation of a sulfenium cation.

The oxidation of benzaldehyde and thirtyfive monosubstituted benzaldehydes²⁵ by BTMACI leads to the formation of the corresponding benzoic acids. The oxidation of [²H] benzaldehyde (PhCDO) indicated the presence of a substantial kinetic effect. The rates of oxidation of *meta*-

and *para*-substituted benzaldehydes were correlated in terms of Charton's triparametric LDR equation, whereas the oxidation of *ortho*-substituted benzaldehyde was correlated with tetraparametric LDRS equations. The oxidation of *ortho*- and *para*-substituted benzaldehydes is more susceptible to the delocalization effect, whereas the oxidation of *meta*-substituted compound displays a greater dependence on the field effect. The positive value of η suggests the presence of an electron-deficient reaction centre in the rate-determining step. It has been suggested that the rate-determining step involves the transfer of a hydride ion from aldehydic C-H bond to the oxidant.

Benzyltrimethylammonium tribromide (BTMAB)

Banerji *et al.* reported the oxidation of aliphatic primary alcohols²⁸, substituted benzyl alcohols²⁹, diols³⁰, α -hydroxy acids³¹, sulfides³², organic acids³³, oxyacids of phosphorus³⁴, thioacids³⁵, aliphatic aldehydes³⁶, aromatic aldehydes³⁷ and benzylamines³⁸ by BTMAB in aqueous acetic acid or DMSO solution. The reactions were first order with respect to BTMAB. Michaelis-Menten type kinetic were obtained with respect to aliphatic alcohols, diols, α -hydroxy acids, formic and oxalic acids, and aliphatic aldehydes, while the order with respect to other reductants was one. Conductivity measurements and kinetic data showed that tribromide ion is the reactive oxidizing species. The reaction rate increased with an increase in the polarity of the medium.

The oxidation of aliphatic alcohols correlated well with Pavelich-Taft's DSP equation⁸. The oxidation of *meta*- and *para*-substituted benzyl alcohols showed excellent correlation in terms of Taft's DSP equation⁹. The *ortho*-compounds correlated best with Charton's triparametric equation¹⁰. The polar reaction constants have negative values, indicating the presence of an electron-deficient carbon-centre in the transition state. The reactions are subject to steric acceleration by *ortho*-substituents and alkyl groups. The oxidation of deuteriated ethanol and benzyl alcohol exhibited a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect, which is independent of temperature. This led to the postulation of a mechanism in which the cleavage of the α -C-H and O-H bonds is almost synchronous. However, the negative polar reaction constants indicated that in the transition state the transfer of a hydride ion from the C-H bond is somewhat ahead of the departure of a proton from the O-H bond (Scheme 5). The value of the equilibrium constant K , may be very small in the oxidation of benzyl alcohol. Hence it is not reflected in the rate laws.

The kinetics of oxidation of five vicinal, four non-vicinal diols, and two of their mono ethers³⁰ were studied. The vicinal diols yielded the carbonyl compounds arising out of

Scheme 5

the glycol bond fission while the other diols yielded the hydroxy-carbonyl compounds. The oxidation of [1,1,2,2-²H₄]ethanediol showed the absence of a kinetic isotope effect. The reaction exhibited a substantial solvent isotope effect. A mechanism involving glycol-bond fission has been proposed for the oxidation of the vicinal-diols.

The oxidation of some α -hydroxy acids³¹ led to the formation of corresponding carbonyl compounds. The oxidation of α -deuteriomandelic acids indicated the absence of a kinetic isotope effect. The rates of substituted mandelic acids correlated well with Hammett's σ -values³⁹ with low negative reaction constants. A mechanism involving the formation of acyl hypobromite derivative in the rate-determining step has been proposed.

The oxidation of some alkyl phenyl sulfides and of *meta*-, *para*- and *ortho*-substituted aryl methyl sulfides was reported by Goel *et al.*³². The rate of oxidation of *para*-, *meta*- and *ortho*-substituted aryl methyl sulfides showed excellent correlation in terms of Charton's LDR/LDRS equations³⁷. The rates of oxidation of alkyl phenyl sulfides yielded an excellent correlation in terms of Pavelich-Taft's dual substituent parameter equation⁸. A mechanism involving a rate-determining electrophilic attack of a tribromide ion on the sulfide-sulfur to yield a bromosulfo-nium ion has been proposed.

In the oxidation of formic and oxalic acids³³ to carbon dioxide, the formation constants of the intermediate complex decrease with an increase in the polarity of solvent, however, their rates of decomposition increase. Mechanisms involving the formation of acyclic and cyclic intermediate in the oxi-

dition of formic and oxalic acids respectively have been proposed.

The oxidation of lower oxyacids of phosphorus³⁴ results in the formation of the corresponding oxyacids with phosphorus in a higher oxidation state. The oxidation of deuteriated phosphinic and phosphorous acids exhibited substantial kinetic isotope effects. The pentacoordinated tautomer of the phosphorus oxyacids was shown to be the reactive reducing species. A mechanism involving a hydride-ion transfer in the rate-determining step has been proposed.

For the oxidation of some thioacids³⁵, to the corresponding disulfide-dimers, the following mechanism has been suggested :

The oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes³⁶ results in the formation of the corresponding carboxylic acids. An analysis of the rate data and the aldehyde hydration equilibrium indicated that the reactive reducing species is the aldehyde hydrate. The rate of decomposition of the complexes exhibited an excellent correlation with Taft's σ values with negative reaction constants. The negative reaction constant points to an electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state. This indicates transfer of a hydride ion from the aldehyde hydrate to the oxidant, in the rate-determining step.

The oxidation of benzaldehyde and thirtyfive monosubstituted benzaldehydes³⁷ by BTMAB in aqueous acetic acid leads to the formation of the corresponding benzoic acids. The oxidation of [²H] benzaldehyde (PhCDO) indicated the presence of a substantial kinetic isotope effect. The rates of oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes were correlated in terms of Charton's LDR/LDRS equations¹⁷. The oxidation of *para*-substituted benzaldehyde is more susceptible to the delocalization effect, then is the oxidation of *ortho*- and *meta*-substituted compounds, which display a greater dependence on the field effect. The positive value of η suggests the presence of an electron-deficient reaction centre in the rate-determining step. The reaction is subjected to steric hindrance by the *ortho*-substituent.

The oxidation of monosubstituted benzylamines³⁸ to the corresponding aldimine has been studied. The oxidation of deuteriated benzylamine (PhCD₂NH₂) exhibited a substantial kinetic isotope effect. The rate of oxidation of *meta*- and *para*-substituted benzylamines showed excellent correlation with both Taft's DSP and Charton's LDR equations. The *ortho*-compound correlated best with LDRS

equation. A mechanism involving an almost synchronous cleavage of the C–H and N–H bond in the rate-determining step has been proposed.

Benzyltrimethylammonium chlorobromate (BTMACB)

The oxidation reactions of aliphatic aldehydes⁴⁰, benzaldehydes⁴¹, amino acids⁴², α -hydroxy acids⁴³, aliphatic alcohols⁴⁴, substituted benzyl alcohols⁴⁵, lower oxyacids of phosphorus⁴⁶ and methionine⁴⁷ have been reported. The reactions are first order with respect to each the reductant and BTMACB. The oxidation of deuteriated acetaldehyde, benzaldehyde, mandelic acid, ethanol, 2-propanol, benzyl alcohol, phosphinic acid and phosphorous acid exhibited substantial kinetic isotope effects. This confirmed the cleavage of the corresponding C–H or P–H bond in the rate-determining step. Conductivity measurements and kinetic data have shown that the reactive oxidizing species is chlorobromate ion.

Bohra *et al.*⁴⁰ reported the oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes by BTMACB in aqueous acetic acid. The product was corresponding carboxylic acid. The rate constants correlate well with Taft's σ^* constants, the reaction constant being negative. The aldehyde hydrate was proposed to be the active reducing species. A mechanism involving a hydride ion transfer from the aldehyde hydrate to the oxidant in the rate-determining step has been suggested.

The rates of oxidation of monosubstituted benzaldehydes⁴¹ were correlated in terms of Charton's LDR/LDRS equations¹⁷. The negative polar reaction constants point to an electron-deficient carbon centre in rate-determining step. A mechanism involving transfer of a hydride ion from benzaldehyde to BTMACB in rate-determining step has been proposed.

The oxidation of some α -amino acids⁴² by BTMACB leads to the formation of corresponding carbonyl compounds. The oxidation of perdeuterioglycine showed the absence of a kinetic isotope effect. Therefore, the α -C–H bond is not cleaved in rate-determining step. The reaction is susceptible to both and steric effects of the substituents. A mechanism involving formation of an acyl hypobromide derivative in rate-determining step has been suggested.

The main product of the oxidation of several α -hydroxy acids⁴³ by BTMACB is the corresponding oxoacid. Absence of a solvent isotope effect indicated the non-involvement of OH or COOH group in the rate-determining step. The oxidation of substituted mandelic acids showed good correlation with Brown's σ^+ values. A mechanism involving a hydride ion transfer from the hydroxy acid to the chlorobromate ion has been postulated.

Rates of the oxidation of aliphatic alcohols by BTMACB⁴⁴ correlated well with Pavelich-Taft's DSP equation⁸. While those of some monosubstituted benzyl alcohols⁴⁵ showed excellent correlation in terms of LDR/LDRS equations of Charton¹⁷. The polar reaction constants have negative values indicating the presence of electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state. The steric reaction constant indicated a steric acceleration. This may well be explained on the basis of high ground state energy of the sterically crowded alcohols. Since the crowding is relieved in the product carbonyl compound as well as in the transition state leading to it, the transition state energies of the crowded and uncrowded alcohols do not differ much and steric acceleration, therefore, results. A rate-determining transfer of a hydride ion from the alcohol to the chlorobromate has been proposed.

The oxidation of three lower oxyacids of phosphorus by BTMACB in 1 : 1 (v/v) has been reported by Bhatt *et al.*⁴⁶. The pentacoordinated tautomer was shown to be the reactive reducing species. A mechanism involving a hydride-ion transfer in the rate-determining step has been proposed.

The oxidation of methionine⁴⁷ leads to the formation of the corresponding sulfoxide. The reaction rates have been determined at different temperature and the activation parameters have been calculated. A mechanism involving the formation of a halogenosulfonium cation in the rate-determining step has been proposed.

Hexamethylenetetramine-bromine (HABR)

The oxidation of primary⁴⁸ and secondary⁴⁹ aliphatic alcohols by HABR has been studied. The reaction is first order with respect to HABR. However, Michaelis-Menten type kinetics were observed with respect to the reductant. The oxidation of deuteriated ethanol and benzhydrol exhibited large kinetic isotope effects. The reaction is susceptible to both polar and steric effects of the substituents. The reaction constants are negative. The authors have shown by spectral and other studies that HABR does not decompose to bromine in acetic acid solutions and retains its integrity. It has been proposed that HABR itself is the reactive oxidizing species in oxidation of alcohols. A mechanism involving a hydride-ion transfer in rate-determining step has been proposed.

The oxidation of five vicinal and four non-vicinal diols by HABR has been reported by Gangwani *et al.*⁵⁰. The kinetics were similar to that observed in the oxidation of alcohols^{48,49}. The vicinal-diols yielded the products arising out of glycol-bond fission while other diols yielded hydroxycarbonyl compounds. Addition of hexamethyl-

enetramine resulted in an increase in the rate-reaction. The oxidation of [1,1,2,2-²H₄]ethanediol showed the absence of a primary kinetic isotope effect. A mechanism involving a glycol-bond fission has been proposed for the oxidation of the vicinal-diols. The other diols are oxidized by a hydride ion transfer mechanism, as are monohydric alcohols.

The oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes⁵¹ also exhibited kinetics similar to that observed in oxidation of alcohols^{48,49}. The presence of a kinetic isotope effect in the oxidation of deuteriated acetaldehyde confirms the cleavage of the aldehydic C-H bond in the rate-determining step. It has been suggested that the mechanism involves formation of an intermediate aldehyde-HABR complex in a rapid pre-equilibrium and its subsequent disproportionation in the slow step *via* a hydride ion transfer.

The oxidation of thioglycolic, thiolactic and thiomalic acids⁵² resulted in the formation of corresponding disulfide-dimers. It has been proposed that the reaction involves formation of sulfenium cation in rate-determining step. The oxidation of lower oxyacids of phosphorus⁵³ also exhibited the usual kinetics. The reaction showed the presence of a substantial kinetic isotope effect. The authors concluded that the pentacoordinated tautomer of the oxyacids is the reactive reductant while the reactive oxidizing species is HABR itself. The oxidation of oxalic and formic acids⁵⁴ to carbon dioxide by HABR exhibited a Michaelis-Menten type kinetics with respect to reductants. The presence of a primary kinetic isotope effect in the oxidation of α -deuteriated formic acid confirms the cleavage of the α -C-H bond in rate-determining step.

The oxidation of nine α -aminoacids⁵⁵ by HABR leads to the formation of the corresponding carbonyl compounds. The reaction is first order each with respect to the amino acid and HABR. The reaction failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. There is no effect of added hexamethylenetetramine on the reaction rates. The oxidation of perdeuteriogylicine shows the absence of a kinetic isotope effect. The effect of solvent composition indicates that the reaction rate increases with an increase in the polarity of the solvent. HABR itself has been postulated as the reactive oxidizing species. The reaction is susceptible both to polar and steric of the substituents. A suitable mechanism has been proposed.

The oxidation of organic sulfides⁵⁶ by HABR, to the corresponding sulfoxides, is first order with respect to HABR. Michaelis-Menten type kinetics were observed with respect to the sulfide. It is proposed that HABR itself is the oxidizing species. The correlation analysis of the rate of the oxidation of thirtyfour sulfides was performed in terms of

various single and multiparametric equations. The best correlation was obtained with Charton's LDR/LDRS equations¹⁷, the polar regression coefficients being negative. The oxidation of alkyl phenyl sulfides exhibited a very good correlation in terms of Pavelich-Taft's equation⁸. A mechanism involving formation of a halogenosulfonium cation in the slow step has been proposed.

Methionine⁵⁷, a sulfur-containing amino acid, behaves like a sulfide towards HABR. The kinetic results observed in this case are similar to those observed in oxidation of sulfides. A mechanism involving the formation of a halogenosulfonium cation in the slow step has been proposed.

The oxidation of a series of substituted benzaldehydes by HABR⁵⁸, exhibited a Michaelis-Menten type kinetics with respect to the aldehydes. It has been found that the equilibrium constant (K) of the intermediate complex is independent of the structure. The rate constant (k_2) of the disproportionation of the intermediate complex correlated well with Charton's¹⁷ LDR/LDRS equations. The polar reaction constants are negative. The oxidation of [²H] benzaldehyde showed the presence of a primary kinetic isotope effect. A mechanism involving transfer of a hydride ion from the aldehydic C–H bond to HABR has been proposed.

Tetrabutylammonium tribromide (TBATB)

Kumar *et al.*⁵⁹ reported kinetics of oxidative regeneration of carbonyl compound from oximes by TBATB in acetic acid-water solutions. The reaction exhibited a second order kinetics. Conductivity measurements indicated that the reactive oxidizing species is the tribromide ion. An analysis of the rates of several aliphatic aldoximes yielded a small positive polar reaction constant. The steric effect played an inhibitory role. Based on these facts, the authors have suggested that the rate-determining step involves a nucleophilic attack of the tribromide ion on the oxime-carbon to yield an almost cyclic activated complex.

The oxidation reactions of aliphatic primary alcohols⁶⁰, substituted benzyl alcohols⁶¹ and α -hydroxy acids⁶² have been studied. The reactions are first order in TBATB. With aliphatic alcohols, Michaelis-Menten type kinetics were observed while benzyl alcohols and α -hydroxy acids exhibited first order dependence. The oxidation of deuterated alcohols and mandelic acid showed the presence of a substantial kinetic isotope effect confirming the cleavage of α -C–H bond in the slow step. The polar reaction constants are negative, indicating the presence of an electron-deficient reaction centre in the transition state. A mechanism, similar to one depicted in Scheme 1 accounts for all the experimen-

tal results.

Oxidation of three lower oxyacids of phosphorus⁶³ leads to the formation of the corresponding oxyacids with phosphorus in a higher oxidation state. The reaction is first order each in TBATB and oxyacids. It has been shown that the pentacoordinated tautomer of the phosphorus oxyacids is the reactive reductant. The oxidation of deuterated oxyacids exhibits a substantial kinetic isotope effect. Rate-determining transfer of a hydride ion in step has been proposed.

The main product of the oxidation of formic and oxalic acids⁶⁴ is carbon dioxide. The reaction is first order with respect to TBATB. Michaelis-Menten type of kinetic were observed with respect to the reductants. The oxidation of α -deuterioformic acid exhibits a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect. Suitable mechanism has been proposed.

The oxidation of six aliphatic aldehydes⁶⁵ by TBATB in aqueous acetic acid resulted in the formation of corresponding carboxylic acids. The reaction is first order with respect to TBATB and the aldehyde. The oxidation of deuterated acetaldehyde (M_c CDO) showed the presence of substantial kinetic isotope effect. The rate constants correlate well with Taft's σ^* value. The reaction constant is negative. A mechanism involving a hydride ion transfer from the aldehyde hydrate to the oxidant in the rate-determining step has been suggested.

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